

**THE THIRD RENAISSANCE AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN
EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM.**

Saparov Bobir

National University of Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT. In this article, the development of the spirit of patriotism in young people is the formation of feelings of social responsibility and belonging, and the elimination of social indifference and indifference on the basis of this, and the social negativity of patriotism, in the conditions of the development of the ideas of cosmopolitanism, the development of the spirit of patriotism in the youth, the development of the spirit of patriotism, the development of the sense of social responsibility and belonging, and the social negativity of patriotism are discussed in this article. designed to introduce reforms aimed at reducing the impact.

Keywords: Third Renaissance, cosmopolitanism, raradigm, patriotism, defense, ethnopsychological, ideology, cognitive, ideal, strong, willful, courageous, faith-believing, righteous, spiritual, political.

In order for us to raise the future generation to be educated, physically and mentally healthy, have intellectual potential or meet the demands of the times, it was necessary to educate the youth who are our future, in the spirit of patriotism. Towards this priority goal, Uzbekistan's "New Uzbekistan Development Plan" for 2022-2026 Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 on the strategy of Recently, in the addresses of President Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and our people on December 20, 2022. "Education of

young people in the spirit of patriotism, sense of citizenship, tolerance, respect for laws, national and universal values, able to resist harmful influences and currents, with firm beliefs and views on life" Various educational, legal and organizational reforms aimed at educating young people in the spirit of patriotism and loyalty to the country are being carried out as a priority goal, many fundamental scientific projects and scientific research works are being carried out is being supported.

The paradigm of national spirituality is a patriotic education focused on unity and solidarity, based on the spiritual values of each nation, based on the images of national heroism, the ideology of historical greatness, and the idea of national values and purity of identity. Because it is valuable in the country for patriotism concepts are required. In other words, in the education of the spirit of patriotism, emphasis is placed on having something valuable and meaningful in one's homeland.

Paradigm - (from the Greek words "template, example") is a set of certain concepts or a template of thinking. Therefore, the paradigm of national spirituality was considered a model or a set of concepts based on national spiritual values. Youth in the spirit of patriotism based on the paradigm of national spirituality. The methods of education are the promotion of historical ideals and their patriotism and heroic deeds, or directing them to their patriotic education based on the ideals of national heroism in education is an important tool. Also, on the basis of creating a template of national spirituality, it will be possible to inculcate patriotism in young people as a moral value or as a virtue [1].

A cognitive approach to educating young people in the spirit of patriotism its effectiveness is considered a process oriented to the knowledge of historical processes. That is, cognitive is a process oriented to knowledge and understanding, inculcating patriotism in students and youth, helping them to understand, and through conscious attitude in them forms patriotic responsibility. In recent years, the state has developed the education system in our country has become the main idea

of the country's policy, ensuring that our children acquire modern knowledge and skills in conditions corresponding to world standards, grow up as physically and spiritually mature people, realize their abilities, talents, and intellectual potential, Great work is being done in them to improve their feelings of loyalty and devotion to the motherland. Uzbekistan is laying the foundation for a new era of renaissance at a time when science has developed, digital economy is widely practiced, and information technology covers all areas.

First of all, it is necessary to clearly reveal the content of the idea of the Third Renaissance and convey it to the minds of all layers of the population, especially the youth. What our ancestors achieved during the past renaissances, their contribution to world civilization, compared with the achievements of other nations and regions, and created one of the world's leading cultures, science, art and literature, advanced social thoughts and views.

The historical conditions and requirements of the first and second renaissances, it is appropriate to justify and prove that the historical conditions and requirements of the New Renaissance are completely different, after assessing its possibilities truthfully.

The Third Renaissance requires a completely new industrial revolution, a technological revolution and a highly developed digital smart economy. At what stages this process will be carried out in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to ideologically connect with the idea of a new renaissance.

Based on the requirement of scientific, scientific-technological supply, all links of the field of education should be continuously reformed. The previous two Renaissances took place on a strong spiritual and ideological basis, primarily on the basis of high morality, justice, thirst for knowledge and tolerance [2].

It can be understood from the above that the Third Renaissance requires us to have a deeper integration with the international community in the fields of science,

technology, information, culture and economy. But this integration process should not be allowed to negatively affect our identity, our language, our national characteristics, our spirituality, and most importantly, the morals of our children. Of this and for that, it demands that the issue of education should be considered as the future of the nation and the country. Convincing young people of a great future, or convincing the government that they are carrying out new reforms, is something that can make them appreciate the motherland. It means the methods of influence on the basis of believing, relating to them [3].

We tried to analyze these issues as part of our research through the following considerations. Formation of patriotism in young people is objective and subjective has factors. At the same time, these factors are based on the following principles that realize patriotic qualities: to feel the responsibility to ensure the development of the homeland and the well-being of the country; to have the skills to understand the essence of high human qualities such as justice, honesty, loyalty, conscientiousness, honor, respectability, and pride. To appreciate patriotism as a high virtue, to realize that this virtue is a high moral duty in protecting the peace of the country and ensuring the security of the homeland [4].

Therefore, patriotism as a moral concept in society formation, it is required to see it not as an activity that can be proved only by taking a weapon, but as a high virtue, a moral criterion. Because the only virtue that exists in young people should be the basis for their patriotism. "Morality is this set of behaviors. Behavior is the form of manifestation of goodness or vice in a particular person. Therefore, each character is a symbol of goodness and nobility or vice and malice. In this respect, they are divided into good and bad. But these do not appear in a person by themselves. Certain conditions and education are necessary for their formation. People are not born evil. Certain conditions make them worse [5].

Education begins from the day of birth and lasts a lifetime continues until the end. It consists of two stages - home and school education." Therefore, the education of young people in the spirit of patriotism begins in the family hearth, and then continues in the educational stages such as kindergarten and school. It is a child in the family learns that the lofty flight of patriotism is not a calling, that it is possible to feel it only after a certain spiritual preparation, that the Motherland should not be seen as "money" or a source of interest. Otherwise, the knowledge given at different stages of education prevents the student from falling into the vortex of self-interest and moral values cannot protect against abuse.

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